

Kinetics and Stereoselectivity of the Inversion of Prochiral Olefins Coordinated to Platinum(II)

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Substitution of *trans*-2-butene for the olefin in $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-am}) (\text{S}, \text{S} \text{ or } \text{R}, \text{R} \text{ trans } 2 \text{ butene})]$ (L-am stands for L-aminocarboxylates) and $[\text{PtCl}_2 (\text{S}, \text{S}-\text{trans } 2\text{-butene})]^-$ in organic solvents exhibits remarkable stereoselectivity so that substitution with retention of configuration proceeds faster than that with inversion. Steric interaction between already coordinated *trans*-2-butene and the incoming *trans*-2-butene seems to be responsible for the selectivity. Substitution of *trans*-2-butene for ethylene in $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-am})\text{-(ethylene)}]$ gives appreciable stereoselectivity at the equilibrated state. Either *S}, \text{S}*- or *R}, \text{R}*-configuration is preferred depending on the variety of the L-aminocarboxylate and those having asymmetric nitrogen on coordination give larger optical yields. The rate to give *S}, \text{S}*-*trans*-2-butene is always greater than that to give *R}, \text{R}*-*trans*-2-butene, regardless of the selectivity at the equilibrated state. The reason of such asymmetric inductions in the equilibrium and in the kinetic process is discussed on the basis of the structure of the platinum(II) complexes.

THE complexes which are dealt with in this paper have molecular asymmetry as shown in Fig 1. The olefins giving rise to such an asymmetry on η^2 -coordination are called prochiral olefins. Propylene, *trans*-2-butene, and 2-methyl-2-butene are prochiral, whereas ethylene, *cis*-2-butene, and 2,3-dimethyl-2-butene are not prochiral. Paiaro and Panunzi first demonstrated the existence of such an optical isomerism by separating the diastereoisomers of *trans* and *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2 (\text{R-or } \text{S-amine})(\text{olefin})]$ ¹. Later the crystal structure of *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2 (\text{S-}\alpha \text{ methylbenzylamine}) (\text{R}, \text{R}-\text{trans}-2\text{-butene})]$ was determined by X-ray diffraction².

Fig 1 Asymmetric coordination of *trans*-2-butene to a square planar platinum(II) complex. *S}, \text{S}* and *R}, \text{R}* denote the absolute configurations of asymmetric carbon atoms in accordance with the sequence rule

Substitution of olefins for the coordinated η^2 -olefin was first studied kinetically for $[\text{PtCl}(\text{acac})(\text{ethylene})]$ (acac stands for enolate anion of acetylacetone) by pmr spectroscopy by Holloway and Forgelman³. However, not much information is available. Stereoselectivity on such a substitution was pointed out by Corradini, Paiaro, and Panunzi in the equilibrium of *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2 (\text{S-amine})(\text{olefin})]$ in organic solvents, *R}*-configuration was preferred by 5 to 50%⁴. Although many studies deal with kinetic stereoselectivity on various reactions of coordinated ligands⁵, no work has ever been published

concerning the kinetic stereoselectivity on the substitution of prochiral olefins

We have synthesised both *trans* (*N}, \text{olefin}*) and *cis* (*N}, \text{olefin}*)- $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-am})(\text{olefin})]$ and separated the diastereoisomers involving *S}, \text{S}* and *R}, \text{R}*-configuration of prochiral olefins by use of the difference in solubility in mixed organic solvents⁶. The ultraviolet absorption and circular dichroism (CD) spectra of a typical complex

Fig 2. Ultraviolet (broken line with dots) and CD (broken line) spectra of partially resolved complex *trans* (*N}, \text{olefin}*) $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-proline}) (\text{S}, \text{S}-2 \text{ butene})]$ in ethanol. The solid line shows the CD pattern of *trans* (*N}, \text{olefin}*) $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-pro})(\text{ethylene})]$.

trans(*N*, olefin) [PtCl(L-prolinate) (*S*, *S* *trans*-2-butene)] is shown in Fig. 2. Both spectra remain unchanged for many hours in acetone. However, the CD peak became smaller on addition of an excess of *trans*-2-butene. The final CD spectra were similar to that of *trans*(*N*, olefin)-[PtCl(L-pro) (ethylene)], which has only one asymmetric centre, L-prolinate. We considered that its CD pattern (solid line in Fig. 2) represented the vicinal effect of L-prolinate in this type of complex⁷. The decrease in CD strength at 26300 cm⁻¹ (380 nm), where the vicinal contribution of L-prolinate has a very small CD strength, should be due to the racemisation of the *trans*-2-butene moiety in *trans*(*N*, olefin)[PtCl(L-pro)(*S*,*S*-2-butene)]⁸.

By measuring the decrease in CD peak height with time, we succeeded in obtaining the rate of inversion of the coordinated *S*, *S*-2-butene, i.e. the epimerisation of the complex. The rate obeyed the second order rate law, Eq. 1.

$$\text{Rate} = k_{2(i \rightarrow d)S} [\text{complex}] [\text{free olefin}] \quad (1)$$

(The *S* in subscript indicates that the initial complex contained *trans*-2-butene in *S*, *S*-configuration.) Thus the epimerisation was understood to proceed via *S_N* 2 mechanism without the solvent path⁹.

Stereoselectivity in the Epimerisation of *trans*(*N*, olefin) [PtCl(L-prolinate) (*trans*-2-butene)]: So far as the inversion of coordinated *S*, *S*-2-butene takes place intermolecularly, the nucleophilic attack of the incoming *trans*-2-butene should be in such an orientation as to give *R*, *R*-configuration. If the *trans*-2-butene come in to give *S*, *S* configuration, the olefin exchange would not result in inversion of configuration, and hence the CD strength would not change. To distinguish such olefin exchanges with retention and inversion of configuration from each other, comparison of the epimerisation rate with that of the isotopic exchange with labelled *trans*-2-butene would be useful. We have synthesised *trans*-(*N*, olefin) [PtCl(L-pro)

(*S*, *S*-2-butene [³H])] and measured the rates of epimerisation by the CD method and that of isotopic exchange by the radiochemical method in acetone. Details of the preparation of the optically active labelled compound and the experimental methods have been published elsewhere¹⁰. Table 1 summarises the second order rate constants of the substitution of *cis*- and *trans*-2-butene for the coordinated *S*, *S*- and *R*, *R*-2-butene [³H] measured by these two methods. Absence of change in ultraviolet absorption spectra of the reaction mixtures during the course of substitution clearly indicated that no other reactions than the olefin exchange took place, i.e. the "chemical composition" of the reaction mixture remained unchanged.

cis-2-Butene is not prochiral and its substitution for the coordinated labelled *S*-butene should give both decreases in CD strength and in specific radioactivity of the recovered complex. Identical *k*₂ values obtained by the two methods show that there is no "local exchange" of methyl protons during the substitution.

On the other hand, *trans*-2-butene gives significantly larger *k*_{2(i → o)}'s than *k*_{2(i → d)}'s. The differences between *k*_{2(i → o)}'s by use of the diastereoisomers is much more modest but appreciable, whereas that between *k*_{2(i → d)}'s is within experimental error.

The reaction mixture contains both diastereoisomers *trans*(*N*, olefin) [PtCl(L-pro) (*S*,*S*-2-butene)] and -[PtCl(L-pro)-(R,R-2-butene)], and each of them undergoes olefin exchange with retention and inversion of the configuration. The *k*_{2(i → o)}'s indicate the sum of both substitutions, whilst *k*_{2(i → d)}'s give the rate with inversion of configuration. Hence individual courses of the substitution can be written as Eqs. 2 to 5.

$$k_{2(i \rightarrow o)S} = k_{2[SS]S} + k_{2[RS]R} \quad (2)$$

$$k_{2(i \rightarrow o)R} = k_{2[RR]R} + k_{2[RS]S} \quad (3)$$

$$k_{2(i \rightarrow d)S} = k_{2[RS]R} + k_{2[RS]S} \quad (4)$$

$$k_{2(i \rightarrow d)R} = k_{2[RS]S} + k_{2[RS]R} \quad (5)$$

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS OF THE SUBSTITUTION OF 2-BUTENE FOR THE COORDINATED *trans*-2-BUTENE IN [PtCl(L PROLINATE)(*S*, *S*- OR *R*, *R*-2-BUTENE)] IN ACETONE¹⁰.

Added 2-butene ^b temp/°C	<i>cis</i>		<i>trans</i>	
	8.0	-20.0	8.0	-20.0
<i>k</i> _{2(i → o)S} /10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	347	70.9 ± 7.6	6.2	0.9
<i>k</i> _{2(i → o)S} /10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	—	70.2 ± 4.1	3.3	5.6
<i>k</i> _{2(i → d)S} /10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	—	—	5.5	(0.9) ^c
<i>k</i> _{2(i → d)R} /10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	—	—	16.6	(2.1) ^c

a) *S* and *R* in the subscripts of *k*'s denote the configuration of coordinated *trans*-2-butene in the original complexes. *cd* and *iso* in the parentheses indicate the methods, i.e. circular dichroism and isotopic exchange, respectively.

b) Concentration range: [2-butene], 0.05 to 0.3 mol. dm⁻³; [complex], 0.0015 mol. dm⁻³.

c) Calculated from only one kinetic run each.

The subscripts in square brackets denote the configuration of coordinated *trans*-2-butenes in the initial and the final complexes: e.g. *k*_{2[RS]S}, second order rate constant for the *S*,*S*-2-butene complex to give *R*,*R*-2-butene complex with inversion of configuration.

The ratio *k*_{2[RS]S}/*k*_{2[RS]R} indicates the stereoselectivity to give the *S*,*S*-2-butene complex in the equilibrated state. This ratio (*K_{RS}*) could be obtained from the *k*₂ values in Table 1, but the experimental error makes the figure ambiguous. However, *K_{RS}* should be reflected in the final CD pattern of the reaction mixture. So far as the vicinal contribution of an L-aminocarboxylate remains unchanged for its complexes containing various olefins, the optical yield at the equilibrated state is given by Eq. 6,

$$p_{\text{eq}} = (\Delta \epsilon_{\text{eq}} - \Delta \epsilon_{\text{ethy}}) / (\Delta \epsilon_{\text{resol}} - \Delta \epsilon_{\text{ethy}}) \quad (6)$$

where the $\Delta \epsilon$'s are the molar CD strengths at the equilibrated state, of the completely resolved *S*,*S*-2-

butene complex and of the ethylene complex of the given L-aminocarboxylate. By use of the observed p_{oa} values (*vide infra*, Table 4), K_{RS} 's are calculated by Eq. 7.

$$K_{RS} = (1 + p_{oa}) (1 - p_{oa}) = k_{2[RS]} / k_{2[SR]} \quad (7)$$

With the aid of Eqs. 2 to 5 and 7, individual k_2 values are calculated as shown in Table 2. The $k_{2[SS]}$ is *ca* twice as large as $k_{2[RR]}$, indicating that the substitution reaction with retention of configuration takes place more readily on *S,S*-2-butene- than on *R,R*-2-butene-complex. Respective comparison of $k_{2[SS]}$ and $k_{2[RR]}$ with $k_{2[SR]}$ and $k_{2[RS]}$ discloses that the substitution with retention of configuration proceeds faster than that with inversion by *ca* 10 and 5 times on *S,S*- and *R,R*-2-butene complex, respectively.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR INDIVIDUAL ROUTES OF SUBSTITUTION, AND THEIR RATIOS (cf. Eqs. 2 to 5)

temp/°C	+ 8 0	-20 0
$k_{2[SS]} / 10^{-8} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	29	5.1
$k_{2[RR]} / 10^{-8} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	14	(1.7) ^c
$k_{2[SR]} / 10^{-8} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	3.1	0.45
$k_{2[RS]} / 10^{-8} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	2.4	(0.46) ^c
$k_{2[SS]} / k_{2[RR]}$	2.1	(3) ^c
$k_{2[SS]} / k_{2[SR]}$ ^a	9.4	11
$k_{2[RR]} / k_{2[RS]}$ ^b	5.0	(3.7) ^c

- a) The original complex contained *S,S*-2-butene (Eqs. 2 and 4)
 b) The original complex contained *R,R*-2-butene (Eqs. 3 and 5)
 c) Calculated from only one kinetic run.

Such a remarkable stereoselectivity can be brought about by either electronic or steric effect. No difference in the electronic effect is, however, expected between the *S,S*- and *R,R*-2-butene complexes for a given substitution. Hence the selectivity must have come from steric interaction between the initial complex and the nucleophile on the formation of transition state. Optically active $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-pro})(\text{trans-2-butene})]$ has three asymmetric centres, *i.e.* the platinum (II)-olefin moiety, asymmetric carbon on L-prolinate, and asymmetric nitrogen brought about by the coordination of amino nitrogen. Asymmetric interaction between the free *trans*-2-butene and the complex to give a stereoselectively formed transition state can take place at these three asymmetric centres. The latter two centres cannot be separated, but their influence is eliminated whenever the L-prolinate ligand is replaced by two unidentates, *e.g.* two chloride ions.

Stereoselectivity in the Olefin Exchange of $[\text{PtCl}_3(\text{S,S-2-butene})]^-$

When $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-pro}) \text{S,S-2-butene}]$ was treated with hydrogen chloride in acetone in the presence of tetraphenylphosphonium chloride, crystalline $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})[\text{PtCl}_3(\text{S,S-2-butene})]^-$ was obtained on addition of hexane. Comparison of the CD spectrum of this complex with that of the initial compound showed that the substitution of chloride took place with full retention of configuration. The product is stable in acetone,

and the CD spectrum remains unchanged for many hours. The ultraviolet absorption and CD spectra are given in Fig 3

Fig 3 Absorption and CD spectra of $[\text{Ph}_4\text{P}][\text{PtCl}_3(\text{S,S-2-butene})]$ in acetone.

Fig. 4. Dependence of the first order rate constants for the racemisation ($k_{2[oa]}$) and for the isotopic exchange ($k_{2[iso]}$) of $[\text{PtCl}_3(\text{S,S-2-butene})]^-$ in acetone in the presence of *trans*-2-butene, upon the concentration of the free olefin, at 8.0°C.

On addition of free *trans*-2-butene in acetone, the CD peak strength decreased and eventually no CD was observed, but the absorption spectrum was not changed. By measuring the CD peak height at 24200 cm^{-1} , the rate of racemisation was measured at -20.0 , -5.0 and $+8.0^\circ\text{C}$. The decrease in specific radioactivity of the complexes precipitated by addition of hexane at appropriate time intervals was also measured side by side. Figure 4 exemplifies the dependence of the observed rate constants k_{obs} measured by the isotopic exchange ($=R/[\text{complex}]$ where R is McKay's rate of isotopic exchange) and by the CD decrease, upon the concentration of free *trans*-2-butene. Apparently no intercept is observed and the second order rate constants k_2 's ($=k_{obs}/[\text{free } trans\text{-}2\text{-butene}]$) are related to the rate constants of individual routes of substitution given in Eqs. 2 and 4. In this complex anion the coordinated S,S - and R,R -2-butene are enantiomeric to each other and $k_{2[SS]}$ and $k_{2[SR]}$ should be equal to $k_{2[RR]}$ and

$k_{2[RS]}$, respectively. Table 3 gives their values together with the activation parameters. The ratio $k_{2[SS]}/k_{2[SR]}$ indicates the kinetic stereoselectivity; the substitution with retention of configuration proceeds faster than that with inversion of configuration by *ca.* 8 times.

Since there is no other asymmetric source than the already coordinated S,S -2-butene, the steric interaction between this ligand and the incoming *trans*-2-butene should be responsible for the selectivity. The pmr spectra of all these diamagnetic complexes give only one signal of methyl protons at the given temperatures, and the coordinated S,S -2-butene must be rotating freely around the Pt-olefin axis. The incoming ligand seems to be subject to less steric hindrance, when it comes in as shown in Fig. 5(B), so that the leave of the S,S -2-butene [3H] results in substitution with retention of configuration. The difference in activation parameters

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS OF THE SUBSTITUTION OF *trans*-2-BUTENE FOR THE S,S -2-BUTENE IN $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{SS-}2\text{-BUTENE})]^-$ IN ACETONE WITH RETENTION ($k_{2[SS]}$) AND INVERSION ($k_{2[SR]}$) OF CONFIGURATION AND THEIR ACTIVATION PARAMETERS.

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	$k_{2[SS]}/10^{-2}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{dm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{2[SR]}/10^{-2}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{dm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$	$\frac{k_{2[SS]}}{k_{2[SR]}}$
+8.0	62.0	8.7	7.2
-5.0	31.7	3.4	9.3
-20.0	10.1	1.3	7.8
$\Delta H^\ddagger$	$36.3 \pm 3.1\text{ kJ. mol}^{-1}$	$37.6 \pm 2.7\text{ kJ. mol}^{-1}$	
$\Delta S^\ddagger$	$-138 \pm 12\text{ J.K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$	$-149 \pm 10\text{ J.K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$	

TABLE 4—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND OPTICAL YIELDS IN THE SUBSTITUTION OF *TRANS*-2-BUTENE FOR ETHYLENE IN $[\text{PtCl}(\text{L-AM})\text{(ETHYLENE)}]$ IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS.^a

L-amb	$t^\circ\text{C}$	solvent	$\frac{k_2(t)}{10^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$	$\frac{p_m\alpha_\lambda}{\%}$	$\frac{k_2[ES]}{10^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$	$\frac{k_2[ER]}{10^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$	$\frac{k_2(t)}{\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$	$\frac{p_e\alpha_\lambda}{\%}$	$\frac{k_2[SE]}{\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$	$\frac{k_2[RE]}{\text{s}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}}$
L-pro	8.0	acetone	very fast	35			6.1	+12	8.3	5.1
N-Me	-27.5	"	(450) ^e	34	(890)	(440)			2.0	0.68
N-Me	8.0	"	fast	53			1.1	-6	2.5	
L-pro	-28.0	"	(75)	49	(115)	(40)				
N-Et										
L-pro	8.0	"	10	50	15	5	slow	0		
N-Br-	8.0	CH_2Cl_2	8.2	24	21.2	13.0	slow	$< \pm 1$		
L-pro	15.0	acetone	8.0	28	18.3	10.3	slow			
			15.3	27	36.0	20.7	0.018	$< \pm 3$	0.024	0.015
N-Bz-			fast	40			1.09	-10	2.0	0.70
L-val	8.0	CH_3CN	fast	39			1.18	-9	2.1	0.77
		AcMthl ^d	fast	35			1.0		(1.9)	(0.66)
L-val	-30.0	acetone		0						
L-ala	-30.0	"		0						
L-hyp	8.0	"	fast	37			10.8	+8	15.8	8.5
N-Me-	8.0	"	fast	32			2.4	-7	3.8	1.7
L-hyp	8.0	"	fast	37			3.8	+6	5.7	3.0
allo-	8.0	"	fast	37						
L-hyp	8.0	"	(20)	31	(40)	(20)				
cis (N, olefin)	8.0	CH_3CN	(50)	39	(90)	(40)				
L-pro	-13.0	acetone	(2)	34	(4)	(2)		-27		

a) *trans* (N, olefin) unless otherwise stated. M stands for mole. dm^{-3} .

b) abbreviations of the aminocarboxylates: pro, proline; Me, methyl; Et, ethyl; Bz, benzyl; val, valinate; ala, alaninate; hyp, *trans*-4-hydroxyproline; *allo*-hyp, *cis* 4-hydroxyproline.

c) The figures in parentheses were obtained by only one kinetic run each.

d) AcMthl, *O*-acetylmenthol (natural, *l*)

Fig. 5. Plausible steric course of nucleophilic attack of *trans*-2-butene upon $[PtCl_3(S,S-2-butene)]^-$ to give *R,R*- (A) and *S,S*-configuration (B).

between k_{21S_1} and k_{21R_1} is not very large, but contribution of the entropy factor is greater than that of the enthalpy factor, as is usual in other stereoselective substitutions.

Asymmetric Induction on the Substitution of *trans*-2-Butene for Ethylene in *trans*(*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(L-am)(ethylene)]$.

The above experiment disclosed that the coordinated *S,S*-2-butene is mainly responsible for the selectivity in the substitution of *trans*-2-butene in acetone. However, the ratio k_{21S_1}/k_{21R_1} for the epimerisation is appreciably larger than that for the racemisation of $[PtCl_3(S,S-2-butene)]^-$. This fact suggests that the coordinated *L*-amino-carboxylate must play some role in the stereoselective epimerisation. In order to find such a contribution, the kinetics of the following reaction was studied in organic solvents.

L-am stands for various *L*-aminocarboxylates shown in Table 4.

Figure 6 shows the change in CD pattern with time in case of *L-am*=*N*-methyl-*L*-prolinatate. The dotted line represents the CD pattern of *trans*(*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(N-Me-L-pro)(ethylene)]$ in which only the vicinal effect of this aminocarboxylate is seen. The plus CD peak at 26300 cm^{-1} corresponds to *S,S*-configuration of *trans*-2-butene. The strength increases first and then decreases to reach the thick solid line at the equilibrated state¹¹. Figure 7 exhibits the change in CD strength at 26300 cm^{-1} with time at +8.0 and -20.0°C. A rapid increase is followed by a slow decrease, and both kinetic processes can be analysed separately.

The first increase reflects more rapid formation of *S,S*-2-butene complex than that of *R,R*-2-butene complex. This process is analysed by the first order kinetic plot, to give $k_{2(t)}$, which increase linearly with increase

Fig. 6. Change in CD spectra of *trans*(*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(N-Me-L-pro)(ethylene)]$ on addition of *trans*-2-butene in acetone at -28.0°C . Dotted line, initial complex; solid line, after 2 min.; broken line with dots, after 4 min.; thick solid line, at the equilibrated state.

Fig. 7. Change in CD strength of the system given in Fig. 6 with time at 26300 cm^{-1} .

in concentration of added *trans*-2-butene. Hence Eq. 9 holds,

$$k_{2(t)} = [-\ln\{(a_t - a_{max})/(a_0 - a_{max})\}]/t / [trans-2-butene] \quad (9)$$

where a 's are observed CD strengths at times indicated by the subscripts. The maximum CD strength a_{max} is related to the kinetic optical yield p_{max} by Eq. 10.

$$p_{max} = (\Delta\epsilon_{max} - \Delta\epsilon_{ethy}) / (\Delta\epsilon_{resol} - \Delta\epsilon_{ethy}) \quad (10)$$

The $\Delta\epsilon$'s are molar CD strengths, i.e., $\Delta\epsilon = a / [\text{complex}]$, at the maximum in Fig. 7, of the initial ethylene complex and of the completely resolved *S, S*- and *R, R*-2-butene complex, respectively.

When individual rate constants to give *S, S*- and *R, R*-2-butene complex by Eq. 8 are written as $k_{2[ES]}$ and $k_{2[ER]}$, respectively, the apparent rate of asymmetric induction $k_{2(d)}$ is related to them by Eq. 11.

$$k_{2(d)} = k_{2[ES]} - k_{2[ER]} \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, they are related to the kinetic optical yield p_{max} by Eq. 12.

$$k_{2[ES]} / k_{2[ER]} = (1 + p_{max}) / (1 - p_{max}) \quad (12)$$

By use of experimental $k_{2(d)}$ and p_{max} , both $k_{2[ES]}$ and $k_{2[ER]}$ are calculated as shown in Table 4 for the complexes containing various L-aminocarboxylates.

The second slow step of Fig. 7 is related to the epimerisation of the *S, S*- and *R, R*-2-butene complex. The rates are, however, much larger than those observed in the earlier part of this study¹⁰. Further, the apparent rate constant $k_{ob(d)}$ obtained by the first order plot on Fig. 7 is independent of the concentration of added *trans*-2-butene. On the other hand, it increases with increase in the initial concentration of complex to give Eq. 13.

$$k_{ob(d)} = k_{2(d)} [\text{complex}] \quad (13)$$

With the aid of a sophisticated kinetic treatment of the system (12), we have found that this process is the epimerisation of *S, S*- and *R, R*-2-butene complex accelerated by the catalytic action of free ethylene liberated by the reaction Eq. 8. Hence Eq. 13 is modified to Eq. 14.

$$k_{ob(d)} = k_{2(d)} [\text{ethylene}] \quad (14)$$

Thus the overall process of the asymmetric induction and the epimerisation of Eq. 8 can be visualised as shown in Fig. 8. The experimental $k_{2(d)}$ is written by Eq. 15,

$$k_{2(d)} = (k_{2[SE]}k_{2[ER]} + k_{2[RE]}k_{2[ES]}) / (k_{2[ES]} + k_{2[ER]}) \quad (15)$$

and the stereoselectivity at the equilibrium state, K_{RS} , is expressed by Eq. 16.

$$K_{RS} = k_{2[RE]}k_{2[ES]} / k_{2[SE]}k_{2[ER]} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 8. Reaction routes of the substitution of *trans*-2-butene for ethylene in *trans* (*N*, olefin) [PtCl (*L*-am) (ethylene)], and the following epimerisation of *trans* (*N*, olefin) [PtCl (*L*-am) (*S, S*- and *R, R*-2-butene)] catalysed by ethylene. The arcs indicate the *L*-aminocarboxylate moiety.

Combination of Eqs. 7, 12, 15 and 16 gives Eqs. 17 and 18.

$$k_{2[SE]} = (1 - p_{eq})k_{2(d)} / (1 - p_{max}) \quad (17)$$

$$k_{2[RE]} = (1 + p_{eq})k_{2(d)} / (1 + p_{max}) \quad (18)$$

All the individual k_2 's obtained from these kinetic treatments are summarised in Table 4 for many platinum(II) complexes containing various L-aminocarboxylates.

Comparison of Various L-Aminocarboxylates as Source of Asymmetric Induction for *trans*-2-Butene. Selectivity in the equilibrated state:—Table 4 clearly indicates that the *cis* (*N*, olefin) complexes give larger p_{eq} 's than the *trans* (*N*, olefin) complexes do. We reported that *cis* (*N*, olefin)-[PtCl (*L*-pro) (*trans*-2-butene)] was not synthesised by the method which successfully gave the corresponding L-alaninate complex and ascribed the difficulty to the steric hindrance brought about by the amino moiety of L-proline and the methyl groups of *trans*-2-butene ligand around the platinum(II).⁷ Studies with molecular models have disclosed that coordinated *S, S*-2-butene involves larger steric hindrance than *R, R*-2-butene does to result in the large minus p_{eq} value (favourable for *R, R*-configuration).

Among *trans* (*N*, olefin) complexes aminocarboxylates with asymmetric nitrogens give large p_{eq} values; *i.e.* L-prolinate, *trans*-4-hydroxy-L-prolinate (L-hyp), *cis*-4-hydroxy-L-prolinate (*allo*-L-hyp), their *N*-methyl derivatives and *N*-benzyl-L-valinate. However, some of them give plus, and some of them give minus p_{eq} 's. Too big a substituent on nitrogen of L-prolinate seems to decrease p_{eq} 's. The reason for such a significant difference cannot be understood by studies with molecular models.

There can be an asymmetric electronic effect from asymmetric nitrogens through the platinum(II) ion.

Stereoselectivity in the substitution of *trans*-2-butene for the coordinated ethylene:—Table 4 shows that those aminocarboxylates having asymmetric nitrogen give significant p_{max} . Here, coordination to give *S*, *S*-configuration is always faster than that to give *R*, *R*-configuration. The ratio $k_{S[ES]}/k_{R[ER]}$ is mostly around 2, and the influence of the solvent seems small. The order of increase in p_{max} is different from that of p_{eq} 's.

Such a dynamic stereoselectivity must be due to the steric interaction between the aminocarboxylate ligands and the nucleophilic *trans*-2-butene. However, detailed structure of the original complex is not known, and we cannot imagine how stressed and deformed are the square planar configurations around platinum(II) even in the ground state. Stereochemistry of the transient state is far beyond our approach at the present stage. Nevertheless our experiments have made it clear that the stereoselectivity in the substitution of *trans*-2-butene for $[PtCl_2(S, S\text{-}2\text{-butene})]^-$ is much more marked than that for $[PtCl(L\text{-}am)(ethylene)]$; *i.e.* the already coordinated *trans*-2-butene brings about larger selectivity than the asymmetric L-aminocarboxylates. They further enabled the discrimination between selectivity at the equilibrated state and that in the course of kinetic processes.

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- e. g.* "Organotransition-Metal Chemistry" (Ed. Y. ISHII and M. TSUTSUI) Plenum Press, New York, U. S. A. (1975), pp. 255, 321.
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- The final CD pattern of a mixture of *trans* (*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(L\text{-}pro)(S, S\text{-}trans\text{-}2\text{-butene})]$ and *trans*-2-butene is not identical with the solid line in Fig. 2. This is related to the stereoselectivity at the equilibrated state, and discussed later in Eq. 6. See also Fig. 6.
- Since only "*trans*"-2-butene is capable of forming asymmetry on η^2 -coordination, "*trans*" is omitted in describing the asymmetrically coordinated *trans*-2-butene.
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- When the vicinal contribution of *N*-methyl-L-prolinate is subtracted from each curve in Fig. 6, the patterns change slightly and an iso-CD point is seen on the zero line.
- It was found that the CD pattern of a mixture of *trans* (*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(L\text{-}alaninate)(ethylene)]$ and *trans*-2-butene was always equal to that of the initial complex in the absence of *trans*-2-butene. Hence L-alaninate gives $p_{eq} = p_{max} = 0$. On addition of this complex to other systems *e. g.* a mixture of *trans* (*N*, olefin) $[PtCl(L\text{-}pro)(ethylene)]$ and *trans*-2-butene, $k_{obs}(d)$ obtained by the first order kinetic plot on the L-prolinate complex is expressed by a modified form of Eq. 13, $k_{obs}(d) = k_2(d)$ [sum of the concentrations of both L-alaninate and L-prolinate complex]. It is seen that the L-alaninate complex functioned as source of ethylene through substitution of *trans*-2-butene. Details of the kinetic studies will be published elsewhere.